

Issues & Challenges before Teaching Personnels in Tribal Areas – A Case Study of an Up-Graded High School

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ABSTRACT

This paper is based on the outcomes of a survey conducted by the scholar for preparation of M.Phil dissertation during September, 2014. The major objective of the study is to examine the impact of development programmes on socio-economic life of tribals. The major thrust of the paper is to find out the reasons for low literacy among the tribal. The findings of the paper is based on the study of Gadapadar Up-Graded High school, situated 5 Kms away from Jeypore block.

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INTRODUCTION

Education is the manifestation of divine perfection already existing in man. (Swami Bibekananda). Education is the training of mind, heart & soul to achieve success. After 67 (Sixty Seven) years of Independence the literacy level is 74.04%. The literacy rate among scheduled casts & tribes remain well below the rest of India's population. The level of literacy among scheduled tribes in Odisha is 52.24% in 2011 census. The low socio economic development & their habitation in various ecological & geo-climatic condition ranging from plains & forests to hills & in accessible areas is the main reason for low level of literacy among them. The overall dropout rate among the STs are 53.68% (source-Statistics of School Education, Govt. of India, 2010-11). Though there are various schemes & Programmes for betterment of the same but grass root level realities are not properly represented. Koraput is one of the tribal dominated district of Odisha, which accounts for 7.27% of total ST population of the State. The overall literacy of the district is 49.87%(2011 census), whereas the literacy level among STs is 18.68%(2001 census). There are 1744 Primary Schools, 854 M.E. Schools & 137 Secondary Schools Plus 35 Colleges. There are 156 numbers of Institutions managed by Welfare Department in the District. Further 450 Hostels are attached by the same Department with School & Mass Education Departmental Institutions. (Source-D.W.O., Koraput). The Govt. provides Stipend, Mid-Day-Meal, Books, Dress materials (2 pairs for primary students), Cycles for

Secondary students(9th & 10th), but despite these incentive there is prevalence of wastage & stagnation. The overall literacy level is not increasing up to the expectation.

Objectives of the Study

To reveal the grass root level realities following variables are studied & analyzed –

1. School Atmosphere
2. Teaching equipments & process
3. Basic amenities & co-curricular activities.
4. Working of Village Education Committee.

Research Questions

1. What are the challenges before the teachers in class room?
2. What are the status of basic infrastructures?
3. What are the impact of local environment upon school administration?

Profile of the School

Started as a Primary School in 1954, Gadapadar UP school was up-graded in the year 2009 as a High School. There are eight class rooms, two toilets, one office room & a Kitchen in the school. Two Hostel rooms are there for Primary Students with intake capacity of 40 boarders. Due to the insufficient class rooms these hostel rooms are also used as Class room in school hours. There are 18 teachers (12 primary & 6

secondary). No peons are there. Two Females are engaged as Cook under Nominal Muster Roll basis. The school has a well protected boundary & well decorated with flower plants.

There are 320 students on the roll in the school, out of which 287 students belongs to primary & 33 students are of

secondary. There are 155 ST students are in primary whereas only five are in secondary. The distribution of students by Class, Gender & Caste/Tribe can be ascertained from Table-1-01 as follows:

Table - 1-01 – Student enrollment in Gadapadar Up-graded High School by Class, Gender & Caste/Tribe

Class	Schedule Tribes			Scheduled Castes			General/SEBC			Grand Total		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
Class-Ist	09	02	11	03	06	09	03	01	04	15	09	24
Class-IInd	14	12	26	08	02	10	02	02	04	24	16	40
Class-IIIrd	18	03	21	12	03	15	05	03	08	35	09	44
Class-IVth	27	11	38	01	00	01	04	06	10	32	17	49
Class-Vth	17	14	31	08	07	15	02	00	02	27	21	48
Class-VIth	04	00	04	04	07	11	05	00	05	13	07	20
Class-VIIth	08	07	15	09	06	15	01	04	05	18	17	35
Class-VIIIth	09	00	09	07	04	11	07	00	07	23	04	27
Primary Total	106	49	155	52	35	87	29	16	45	100	187	287
Class-Xth	01	02	03	04	09	13	01	03	04	06	14	20
Class-Xth	01	01	02	03	05	08	02	01	03	06	07	13
Secondary Total	02	03	05	07	14	21	03	04	07	12	21	33
Grand Total	108	52	160	59	49	108	32	20	52	199	121	320

Procedure of Data Collection

The field work conducted for the purpose was participatory in nature. The researcher visited the school during the month of September, 2014 & December, 2014 for survey in connection with preparation of M.Phil dissertation & for the particular seminar. There the interaction between the Teachers, Students (both boarders & day scholars) was conducted. In the focus group discussion with the villagers their opinion about school & its management was ascertained.

Findings of the Study

Condition of Infrastructure

Though the accommodation facility in the school is insufficient, the rooms are in good condition. The office room is partitioned with a curtain to be used as class room. The toilets are well functioning but its doors need repair. There is no play ground in the school. The courtyard of the school is not well maintained which creates problem during rainy season.

There is need for three additional rooms & one Auditorium for proper accommodation of classes in the school.

Co-Curricular Activities in the School

The school organizes its annual function by charging fee from the students. National festivals like Republic Day & Independence day, festivals like Ganesh Puja & Sharaswati Puja are regularly organized. The school also sponsors 2 students annually for science seminars. The sports facility in the school is poor.

Management of the School

The school is managed by its Headmistress Mrs. Kumudini Devi. But the functioning of a local office "Anchalika Sadhan Kendra" in the school campus affects proper functioning of the school. A teacher is in charge of the Hostel. Except to this teacher, no other teacher resides on the school campus.

Health Facilities & Check-Ups

There is no First Aid Box in the School. Health Check-up is done annually to achieve the target only.

Problems & Demand of Students

Though there is the provision of multi language teacher, the school does not have this. This problem severally affects the Primary Students. Further, the language of coastal belt teachers is different from that of local language; so it creates a laughing situation for them. As the toilets are remodeled on a congested manner, the Day Scholar students do not use it properly. Further the toilet for the both boys & girls are constructed side by side it hampers privacy of the girls. They are also demanding remedial classes & tuition, spoken English teaching & sports equipment.

Outcomes of FGD with Teachers

Focus Group discussions with the teachers were organized on the various issues like student's absenteeism, demand of students, infrastructure & management of the school. The discussion revealed the following results –

1. Engaging pupils in domestic work & lack of farsightedness towards girl's education after puberty is the main cause of student's absenteeism.
2. The rate of stipend is low in comparison the money they have to spend to acquire a caste certificate. There is prevalence of Bribe.
3. The students are not properly cleaned which creates bad odor in classroom. It affects the study atmosphere in the school.
4. The students belonging to poor categories have to attend the school in empty belly. A breakfast provision may be made for the students to make them attractive into the class.
5. Tutorial classes have to be arranged to clear the doubts of the students. Spoken English classes & remedial classes need to be organized & special allowance may be provided to the teachers for the same.

6. District wise syllabus may be prepared according to the need of local conditions.
7. Local language training may be provided to them.
8. Audio-visual facility may be provided in tribal areas at least once in a month.
9. Through stage shows awareness campaigns may be organized to make aware the tribal as they are imparting more focus on employment of their ward instead schooling.
10. The scholar has come across instances where, the teachers of residential sevashrams are inducting students from non-residential schools who are reading in higher classes, only to increase the strength of students in these schools

SUGGESTIONS

The following points are suggested for better education –

1. As there is severe unemployment after education, craft centred education especially in tribal areas may be introduced. After the completion of schooling the students should be provided with bank finance to run their own business.
2. Further some topics from the content maybe changed which are not of useful. For example works by the kings of England etc. which does not helps the students in any way.
3. The capacity building training provided by the govt. to the educated tribal mass is consists of only some months. This should be checked.

4. The vicious circle of poverty in tribal society can be checked by approving their craft industries & Ayurvedic knowledge. This type of education may be introduced.

If with courage & wisdom her leaders have the sagacity to work with the aid of science, there is no reason why India should remain forever poor.

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